

Exploring the Impact of Perceived Parental Style and Emotional Intelligence Level on Attitudes Towards Criminal Behaviour

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.21171183 | ISSN: 2977-1676

The Journal of
Crime & Justice
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www.journalcjd.org

British Library Registered ISSN: 2977-1676

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21171183>

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The Journal of
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Abstract

Exploring the relationships between perceived parental style, emotional intelligence and attitudes towards criminal behaviour is important for understanding factors associated with improving interventions and preventing criminal actions. The current study examined whether perceived parental style (authoritarian, authoritative and permissive) and emotional intelligence jointly influenced adult criminal behaviour attitudes, whilst also controlling for age and gender. 102 participants completed questionnaires regarding the way in which they were parented, their emotional intelligence level (The Schutte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test) and their attitudes surrounding offending. A multiple regression analysis was conducted examining the relationships between all variables. The overall regression was not significant; however, correlations were identified between criminal behaviour attitudes and both authoritarian and authoritative parental styles, as well as between age and offending attitudes. These findings suggest that relationships between these variables may be complex and influenced by individual differences and life experiences. Future research using longitudinal designs may provide greater insight into how these relationships develop over time.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Within forensic psychology, understanding potential predictors of criminal behaviour is essential for ensuring the success rates of preventative measures and further understanding the variation within criminal acts, and the motives for such behaviour (Patle et al., 2025). Identifying these predictors assists in the development of preventative interventions, therefore, psychological research heavily focuses on experiences that may contribute to later offending (Efthimiou et al., 2024), including general attitudes towards criminal behaviour (Tiratelli, 2025). The aim of this study is to explore whether perceived parental style and emotional intelligence interact to form attitudes towards criminal behaviour, whilst giving particular attention to the effects of age and gender.

1.2 Parenting Styles

All individuals begin their lives as infants, making the experience of being parented by older caregivers near-universal. How this looks varies immensely depending on a range of factors such as age of parents, familial background, beliefs, intelligence, poverty, education, and opportunities (Doepke & Zilibotti, 2024). Psychological exploration of early human experiences has been documented for centuries and is closely linked with research in forensic based topics (Carlos, 2024; Jahic et al., 2021). The way in which a person is parented in their early life can affect their thinking and behaviours for the rest of their lives, as observed in generational studies (Metzler et al., 2016; Nichol, Curley & Sime, 2025).

Diana Baumrind first introduced the idea of three specific parental styles in 1963, which are still frequently used within the psychological field when assessing the impacts of parenting. She categorised the parental styles as authoritarian, authoritative and permissive. Authoritarian parenting is described as being strict and rigid, expecting consistent obedience whilst providing minimal, if any, emotional support. Corporal punishment may be used in tandem with uninformative, demanding statements such as 'because I said so' or 'eat what I give you' (Jadon & Tripathi, 2017). Baumrind (1963) found that children belonging to authoritarian families appeared more moody and less cheerful with an increased likelihood of depression over time. Since then, many studies exploring authoritarian parenting have reported long-term adverse effects on children's self-esteem and psychological well-being (Chen, 2022; Rezai Niaraki & Rahimi, 2013), raising concerns about its suitability for promoting healthy psychological development into adulthood. It has also been reported that these effects may differ in relation to gender, with boys being more prone to externalising behaviours such as aggression, whereas girls may

demonstrate increased levels of internalising behaviours like anxiety or depression (Haahr-Pedersen et al., 2021; Leban, 2021).

In contrast, some parents follow a more permissive approach. Defined initially by Baumrind (1963) as a low-demand, high-responsiveness style of parenting, where parents are nurturing and warm towards their children, but lack clear expectations, boundaries and demands. The relationship between child and parent may be referred to as a 'best friend' scenario (Ashraf, Khan & Atta, 2024). Whilst there have been small correlations found between increased self-esteem and permissive parenting due to the high warmth factor (Pinquart & Gerke, 2019), many studies report permissive parenting to be associated with higher rates of aggression (Batoool, 2013), less respect for rules and boundaries (Mutunga, Gantai & Mbirirhi, 2023), and lower emotional intelligence in adulthood (Wischerth et al., 2016). Gender appears to potentially moderate some of these effects, with boys subject to permissive parenting demonstrating greater impulsivity and rule-breaking, while girls may show increased emotional sensitivity and relational difficulties (Parent et al., 2011). However, Lassi (2025) reported permissive parenting produced positive behavioural outcomes within the participants in their study. This study does appear to be an anomaly among the literature, as most indicate a more adverse outcome from a permissive approach to parenting (Harjis, 2025; Faught, Phillips & Conners, 2022). Considering this new finding within the parental approaches research, further exploration is required to fully understand the impacts of each of Baumrind's methods of child rearing.

Authoritative parenting is considered to be the ideal approach with the most positive outcomes within psychological research (Tiwari, 2022; Kong & Yasmin, 2022). It involves providing clear, firm boundaries but also being warm and nurturing. The adult is in charge, but the child has a voice and some guided independence. Higher academic achievement, and greater self-efficacy have been observed in adolescents who perceive their parents to have an authoritative style (Hayek et al., 2022). Specifically, differences across genders have been observed, with girls showing stronger developments in emotional regulation and empathy (Piko & Balazs, 2012), and boys demonstrating improvements in problem-solving and assertiveness (Sochukwuma et al, 2020). This demonstrates children parented in this manner are at a greater likelihood of success, happiness and positive self-esteem later in life (Georgievska et al., n.d).

The literature surrounding parental styles in more recent years has started to consider a term known as gentle parenting (Ockwell-Smith, 2023) which follows similar principles as authoritative parenting. However, it is not recognised as an official psychological parental style, but rather a parenting philosophy. The key differences are a lack of punishment within gentle parenting and increased dignity

and respect towards the child, as an individual would towards another adult, whereas authoritative parenting has consequences, but they are generally fair and logical (Walters, 2024). Researchers have debated which has the most positive overall outcomes and the answer is still unclear (Pezalla & Davidson, 2024; Awiszus, Koenig & Vaisarova, 2022). Finally, the concept of neglectful parental style was introduced in 1983 by Maccoby and Martin with a lack of attunement to the child's physical and emotional needs being the main categorisation (Maccoby & Martin, 1983). For the present study, gentle and neglectful parenting will not be assessed.

It is also important to consider that perceptions of parenting styles may vary across generations (Ghorbani et al., 2021), as parenting norms and societal expectations have changed over time. For example, authoritarian parenting style was once more commonly accepted as the norm (Garcia et al., 2020), therefore older generations may perceive it differently as it was a usual experience for them and their fellow peers at that time. However, this does not diminish the impact such parenting may have had, it simply offers explanation regards the perceptual changes over many generations. Thus, retrospective accounts of parenting may be influenced by both generational context and memory reconstruction (Liu et al., 2023).

1.3 Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence (EI), first introduced by Salovey and Mayer (1990), refers to the ability to conduct accurate reasoning about emotions of oneself and others (Mayer, Roberts & Barsade, 2008). EI is generally considered to encompass a range of human abilities - self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy and social skills - which are independent of standard intellectual ability (Derksen, Kramer & Katzko, 2002). Studies report very low correlations between EI and intelligence quotient (IQ) scores (Checa & Fernandez-Berrocal, 2015), reiterating the distinctness of these two concepts. IQ refers to numerical representation of human intelligence, determined via a standardised test to examine an individual's cognitive abilities such as reasoning, problem-solving, memory, and abstract thinking (Johnson, 2024). It is, however, largely debatable how affective the test is at accurately assessing human intelligence as it can be considered quite rigid in its criteria, with some arguing that it reflects social class background more appropriately than intelligence (Richardson, 2002).

Typically, EI is assessed using self-report measures, for example the Schutte Self Report Emotional Intelligence Test (SSEIT) (Schutte et al., 1998). Extensive research suggests the scale to have high reliability and validity in the assessment of EI as it incorporates four main sub-factors, found to be relevant across different cultures (Hussein, Acquah & Musah, 2019). However, as with all self-report

scales, the reliability of participant memory recall and honesty is questionable, making any assessment of EI potentially inaccurate. Discrepancies also arise between the model of EI in which SSEIT is based upon (Salovey & Mayer, 1990) as the model has six sub-categories and the self-report test has only four. Gignac et al., (2005) suggest that the SSEIT does not fully capture the original model, despite its validity in measuring EI, as some components are missing or blended. Regardless of this, they also report the SSEIT to be effective at measuring 'typical' behaviour rather than just when an individual is under pressure and it is easy to use, making it widely accessible. Gender differences are also apparent among EI research, with females generally demonstrating increased levels of empathy and emotional perception, and males showing stronger emotional regulation in some contexts (Karimpour et al., 2019)

EI is reported to be relevant in many areas of adult behaviours, including risky driving, pro-health measures and misuse of substances (Brackett, Mayer & Warner, 2004; Hayley et al., 2017; Sygit-Kowalkowska, Sygit & Sygit, 2015). Therefore, EI may be relevant among criminal behaviours and the processing beneath the behaviour, making it essential to explore.

1.4 Parenting, Emotional Intelligence and Behaviour

In the exploration of adolescents EI development and the simultaneous parental style at home, it was concluded that the method of parenting does impact EI development (Nastas & Sala, 2012). Specifically, authoritative parental style is believed to increase the development of EI with positive associations reported (Al-Elaimat, Adheisat & Alomyan, 2018). However, these relationships are not necessarily uniform across gender; some evidence suggests females may experience greater benefit in terms of emotional awareness, whereas males may demonstrate more variation in behavioural regulation outcomes (Zukauskiene, Malinauskiene & Erentaite, 2011). Authoritarian and permissive styles are consistently associated with lower EI in young adults and adolescents (Harjis, 2025), with some researchers arguing that permissive parental style has slightly higher EI overall than authoritarian (Cameron, Cramer & Manning, 2020). Some research suggests that level of parental education as a whole could be a mediating factor in these relationships, indicating a potential closer link with general intelligence alongside EI (Argyriou, Bakoyannis & Tantaros, 2016). Furthermore, the authoritarian parents are themselves associated with lower EI (Singh, 2025) which encourages debates whether the impact is from the parenting itself or observational learning. According to Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977), children learn via observation and imitating adult behaviours, which may blur the distinction between the effects of parental style and observational learning on EI development.

Exploring differences across cultures is important when assessing the relationship between parental style and levels of EI as Yadav et al., (2021) found that authoritarian parenting correlated with the highest EI scores among their participant pool of students in India unlike most of the European research. Reports also demonstrate that authoritarian parenting does not have the same negative impact on mental health in eastern cultures as often found elsewhere (Singh, Gera & Behmani, 2021). This discrepancy may reflect cultural differences in the interpretation of authoritarian behaviours, where strictness may be perceived as structure and care rather than control and rigidity (Pearlman, 2024). As the present study focuses on participants resident of the UK, the western world literature is most relatable.

The links found between EI and parenting styles have been explained throughout the literature. Authoritarian parenting has been associated with mental health conditions such as depression and anxiety, which may hinder EI development due to chronic activation of the stress-response systems (Carbonella, 2015). Furthermore, researchers argue that authoritarianism is the most likely parenting style to be related to symptoms of depression due to the dominating, criticising and disapproving nature of the method of parenting; compounded by the lack of warmth and care the child receives (King, Vidourek & Merianos, 2016). Negative associations between authoritative parenting style and depressive symptoms are also apparent in the literature (Piko & Balazs, 2012), which may partially explain the increase in EI levels among children with authoritative parents. Research suggests depressive symptoms may hinder or interrupt the development of EI contributing to the explanation of this relationship (Okasha et al., 2022; Zoromba et al., 2022). Barton and Hirsch (2015) suggested the presence of relationships between permissive parenting and negative mental health, mediated by increased academic entitlement. This may be attributed to the high warmth factor but also the low demands expected by permissive parents. Due to the associations found within the literature exploring parental style and EI, it is useful to continue examining the interactions between both concepts to enable informed interventions targeting criminal behaviours.

1.5 Emotional Intelligence and Criminal Behaviour

Lower EI is more prevalent among offender populations compared to nonoffenders according to psychological literature (Megreya, 2015; Sharma et al., 2015). As EI encompasses empathy, emotional regulation, decision-making and impulse control, deficits in EI may fundamentally involve reduced empathy and impaired regulation. Research suggests that maladaptive emotional regulation increases aggression, which subsequently increases the likelihood of offending behaviour (Robertson, Daffern & Bucks, 2014). Furthermore, emotional dysregulation can present as longer periods of negative

emotional states, an important risk factor when considering criminal behaviours (Day, 2009). When an individual feels prolonged difficult emotions with an inability to regulate them, the behaviour administered can represent the emotion they are feeling e.g. anger may manifest as aggression. Empathy is also relevant in aggressive behaviour; specifically, cognitive empathy rather than affective empathy (Gantiva, 2018). Cognitive empathy refers to an ability to accurately identify the emotions of others (Lamm, Batson & Decety, 2007). Higher cognitive empathy abilities have been significantly associated with less aggressive behaviour, potentially mediated by self-regulation capacities. Deficits in decision-making and impulse control may further contribute to offending behaviour, as individuals with lower EI may act on immediate emotional responses without considering the consequences of their actions. Furthermore, it is particularly relevant to consider gender differences among offenders, in relation to EI, as males are often overrepresented among offender research (Hannon & Dufour, 1998), which could partially reflect the differences within emotional regulation and behavioural expression.

Violent offending in particular has concrete associations with limited EI, especially involving hostility towards individuals based on protected characteristics such as religion, sexual orientation, age, social class, and gender (Porche, 2016). The inability to recognise and understand others' views and emotions can prevent the acceptance of different lifestyles, unfamiliar to oneself. Emphasised further by increased levels of aggression and impulsivity and decreased empathic abilities. A specific EI programme aiming to reduce violence among adolescents suggests that when EI increased, aggression and violence decreased across both genders (Garaigordobil & Pena-Sarrionandia, 2015). However, social interaction abilities, attention and emotional clarity increased significantly greater for boys than girls, suggesting correlations between EI and offending may differ across genders. Furthermore, in school-related violence, the main dimension of EI predicting violent behaviours was limited emotional regulation (Estevez, Jimenez & Segura, 2019). Therefore, exploring which factors determine the 'aggressor' mentality is extremely relevant.

Whilst much of the literature focusses on violent offending, the associations between EI and criminality extend beyond aggression to include non-violent behaviours such as risky decision-making, substance misuse and theft (Knight, 2005). Moreover, recidivist offenders have been found to score significantly lower on EI and measures of susceptibility to embarrassment compared to first-time offenders (Emekpo, Obi-Nwosu & Onuoha, 2024), suggesting that EI levels may be related to persistent patterns of offending. However, this is not an entirely straightforward relationship, as not every offender demonstrates deficits in EI (Omand, 2020). Some offenders may possess adequate or amplified emotional skills, which can be used to manipulate or deceive, particularly witnessed in individuals with

traits of narcissistic personality disorder (NPD) and psychopathy (Nagler et al., 2014). Additionally, gender may further complicate these findings as the characteristics can present differently across sexes (Weidmann et al., 2023); for example, NPD is most prevalent among men (Grijalva et al., 2015; Ingersoll et al., 2017), but psychopathy affects both genders, with women showing increased flirtatious, and self-injurious behaviour than men, where manifestations may be manipulative in manners closer related to illegal schemes and fraud (Wynn, Hoiseth & Pettersen, 2012). A difficulty arises in most assessments of EI and offending relying on self-report measures, which are known to be problematic and unreliable, increasingly so for this particular group of participants skilled in manipulation. Therefore, although EI appears to play a role in criminal behaviour, it is a complex relationship and may differ depending on nature of offense and individual differences (Sharma et al., 2015). The complexities of this relationship emphasise the importance of how developmental factors, such as parenting, may influence EI and subsequent offending behaviours.

Parenting may not be the only influence in the development of EI. While much of the literature emphasises that EI develops during childhood and adolescence, other factors later in life – such as peer groups, employment, maturity and personal relationships – can further shape EI (Chapman & Hayslip, 2006). Research indicates that EI may continue to increase with age (Scheibe & Carstensen, 2010; Sharma, 2017), even into established adulthood, suggesting that parental influences may play a smaller role in the fully developed EI of an adult (Mayer et al., 2000; Mayer, Salovey & Caruso, 2008). Conversely, some studies report a decline in certain aspects of EI in later life, indicating that EI is a dynamic, lifelong process (Sze et al., 2012). Considering this, the relationship between EI and criminal behaviour may not be uniform across age groups, highlighting the importance of considering age when exploring these concepts.

1.6 Parenting Styles and Criminal Behaviour

Early childhood experiences are well-documented to shape behaviour into adulthood (Dewey, 2020). In particular, parenting behaviours, including levels of care, warmth, control and responsiveness, are central to the types of early experiences children have and may contribute to trauma exposure (Felitti et al., 1998). Consequently, childhood adversity can have profound effects on an individual's well-being, mental health and emotional development (Hughes et al., 2016). Supporting this, extensive research has demonstrated a strong relationship between childhood trauma and later offending. In the UK context, recent statistics suggest 51.6% of incarcerated men have experienced at least one adverse childhood experience, with likelihood of criminal activity increasing when number of adverse experiences increase (Quigg et al., 2025). This emphasises the relationship between early experiences

and criminal offending, highlighting the need to explore the underlying mechanisms within maladaptive behaviours, including perceived parental style.

Different parental styles appear to influence offending behaviours in distinct ways (HM Inspectorate of Probation, 2023). In particular, authoritarian parenting, characterised by low warmth and high control, has been associated with the development of callous-unemotional and antisocial traits (Wang et al., 2021; Ehrensaft et al., 2003; Narusyte et al., 2007), which are commonly observed in offender populations (Cale et al., 2015). The lack of warmth within this style may hinder emotional development and increase callousness, making criminal acts more likely (Bisby, Kimonis & Goulter, 2017). Encouraging emotional suppression or fear-based compliance – as observed in high-control and low-warmth home environments – limits the child’s ability to freely express their feelings and guides behaviour through punishment, rather than understanding (Schaffer, Clark & Jeglic, 2008). Therefore, minimal opportunities arise for the child to develop emotional understanding and empathy, disrupting their internalised moral reasoning (Eisenberg & Morris, 2001). Thus, deficits in emotional understanding and moral internalisation may reduce inclination toward prosocial behaviour and increase vulnerability to antisocial and potentially criminal actions.

In contrast, permissive parenting, which combines high warmth with low demandingness, has recorded associations with lower levels of callous traits (Eck, 2024); however, it may simultaneously increase aggressiveness due to limited experience with boundaries and rules (Masud et al., 2019; Dacheng, 2022). This may be attributed to strong empathy development within the high-warmth factor, minimising callousness, but a lack of structure may increase impulsivity and weaken self-regulation and the understanding of consequences. The underdeveloped impulse control and self-regulation may lead to greater externalising behaviour, such as aggression. Although emotional warmth may support aspects of emotional development, insufficient behavioural regulation may result in difficulties managing emotions effectively, particularly when faced with conflicts or frustration.

Authoritative parenting, characterised by both high warmth and high structure, is widely considered a protective factor in relation to emotional development and offending behaviour (Goering & Mrug, 2021). This may be attributed to parental emotional availability, which facilitates the development of empathy and emotional regulation (Kang & Guo, 2021) alongside consistent and fair boundary setting that assists in limiting impulsivity (Mangestuti, 2025; Ha & Doan, 2026). The combination of supportive and structured parenting within the parent-child relationship, may therefore mitigate the likelihood of engagement in criminal behaviour, by promoting well-developed emotional and self-regulatory capacities.

The impact of parental style on later offending may also be affected by age and life experiences beyond childhood (Liu & Lachman, 2019). As individuals move into middle adulthood, the direct influence of parenting may decrease (Copp, Mumford & Taylor, 2025), with factors such as personal relationships, career experiences, and becoming a parent oneself potentially reshaping behavioural and emotional tendencies. However, early adversity or extreme parental experiences, including neglect, may continue to shape behaviour well into adulthood (Slicker et al., 2005), indicating that the effect of parental style is not uniform across the lifespan. This suggests that while perceived parental style can contribute to behavioural outcomes, including criminality, other experiential factors make its long-term impact complex and highly individual.

Overall, these findings suggest the relationship between parenting styles and behavioural outcomes is complex rather than linear, with variations in warmth and behavioural expectations influencing the development of emotional regulation (King, 2023). In particular, these parental techniques may significantly contribute to shaping emotional intelligence, including the ability to perceive, understand and regulate emotions. Considering EI has been associated with behavioural control and social decision-making, it may represent a key mechanism through which parental styles influence attitudes towards criminal behaviour. However, regardless of the well-established associations, research is yet to fully explore the way in which perceived parental style and EI operate together in predicting how individuals view offending behaviours.

1.7 Research Gap

Extensive research supports the notion that both perceived parenting style and emotional intelligence independently influence behavioural outcomes related to criminality (Megraya, 2015; HM Inspectorate of Probation, 2023). However, very few studies have examined how these factors interact together in forming attitudes towards criminal behaviour (Hoeve et al., 2009; Megreya, 2015). Understanding the mechanisms through which parenting and EI jointly influence attitudes is important for informing preventative strategies and rehabilitative interventions. Therefore, there is a clear need for research that investigates the combined effects of parental style and EI on offending-related attitudes.

1.8 Study Aims

The present study aims to explore and answer the following research questions:

1. Does lower emotional intelligence predict more tolerant attitudes towards criminal behaviour?

2. Does authoritarian parental style predict less tolerant attitudes towards criminal behaviour?
3. Does permissive parental style predict more tolerant attitudes towards criminal behaviour?
4. Does authoritative parental style predict less tolerant attitudes towards criminal behaviour?

A multiple regression analysis will be conducted to determine any unique factors within these relationships.

Chapter 2: Method

2.1 Design

The current study used a within-subject quantitative correlational design with attitudes to criminal behaviour as the outcome variable. There are four predictors of the outcome variable included: emotional intelligence level, perceived parental style, age and sex.

2.2 Participants

102 (Male: 9, Female: 92, Non-Binary: 1) participants agreed to provide answers to the questionnaires, recruited via an anonymous link advertised on social media (Facebook, Instagram and LinkedIn). All comments were 'turned off' on social media advertisements to uphold anonymity of all participants.

2.3 Materials

The study provided a consent form, a participant information sheet – explaining what could be expected – and a debrief sheet providing further detail on the study and self-help guides. The questionnaire contained six questions relevant to the outcome variable and the four predictors:

Two demographic questions acquiring the sex and age of all individuals (appendix 1, x.1). To obtain answers exploring participants' emotional intelligence level, The Schutte Self Report Emotional Intelligence Test (SSEIT) (Schutte et al., 1998) was incorporated into the questionnaire (appendix 1, x.2). The SSEIT contained 33 items with a higher score representing a higher emotional intelligence level. All items were answered on a 5-point Likert scale between 1 and 5, (1 = strongly agree, 5 = strongly disagree).

For assessing participants' attitudes towards criminal behaviour, a scale rating the severity of specific criminal actions (appendix 1, x.3) was included. This element of the questionnaire contained 13 items where each item was scored individually on a 5-point Likert scale between 1 and 5 (1 = not severe, 5 = very severe). Overall lower scores indicated increased tolerance for criminal behaviours.

The Parental Approaches Questionnaire (PAQ) (appendix 1, x.4) was developed for the present study, to explore perceived parental styles in an ethical manner, increasing suitability for undergraduate research projects. The scale consisted of 17 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (never)

to 5 (all of the time). Items were categorised in three subscales: Authoritative (6 items), Authoritarian (5 items) and Permissive (6 items). The subscale scores were calculated by combining item responses within each category, where higher scores represented greater experiences of the corresponding parental style. Internal consistency was assessed using Cronback's alpha. Acceptable internal consistency was observed for the authoritative ($\alpha = .94$), authoritarian ($\alpha = .75$) and permissive ($\alpha = .67$) subscales (see appendix 2 for SPSS output).

2.4 Procedure

Ethical approval was first obtained from the university before commencement of the current study. All participants accessed a Qualtrics weblink on the social media advertisement they witnessed. First, they read the participant information sheet and consent form before accepting the conditions. After this, they were presented with two demographic questions regarding age and gender. Following on from that, each participant answered three questions, with sliding-scale response options, relating to emotional intelligence, perceived parental style and attitudes towards criminal behaviour. Once content with their responses, a final question confirming their consent to submit was completed. The final screen present for each participant was a debrief explaining the rationale behind the study, researcher contact details, and some self-help weblinks for anyone affected by the questions asked.

Chapter 3: Results

The means and standard deviations of all variables was obtained via SPSS version 31 (see table 1).

Variable	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)
Criminal Behaviour Attitudes	4.13	.57
Age	39.05	12.76
Emotional Intelligence score	2.71	.63
Permissive Parental Style	2.25	.84
Authoritarian Parental Style	2.79	1.10
Authoritative Parental Style	3.12	1.28

Table 1: the Means and Standard Deviations of All Variables (see appendix 1 for SPSS output).

A Pearson's correlation was conducted using SPSS version 31 to examine the presence of any relationships between the predictors (see table 2).

	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.
1.Sex							
2.Age	.17						
3.Criminal behaviour attitudes	.06	.25*					
4.Emotional intelligence score	.09	-.12	-.10				
5.Permissive parental style	.12	-.10	.09	-.00			
6.Authoritarian parental style	.17	-.11	-.20*	.17	.26**		
7.Authoritative parental style	-.15	-.05	-.21*	-.15	.25*	-.56**	

Table 2: Pearson's Correlations Between Perceived Parental Style, Age, Sex, Emotional Intelligence Scores and Criminal Behaviour Attitudes (see appendix 2 for SPSS output).

The two-tailed Pearson's correlation demonstrated no evidence of collinearity but a weak, positive and significant relationship between age and attitudes towards criminal behaviour ($r = .25$, $p = .035$) was revealed suggesting that stricter attitudes towards criminal behaviour is closer associated with increased age.

There was also a significant, weak and negative relationship found between criminal behaviour attitudes and both authoritarian parenting style ($r = -.20$, $p = .044$), and authoritative parenting style (r

= -.21, $p = .033$), suggesting that those who experienced either authoritarian or authoritative parenting had more tolerant attitudes towards criminal behaviour.

A multiple regression analysis (see appendix 2, y.3 for SPSS output) was conducted to examine whether age, sex, emotional intelligence level, and perceived parental style (permissive, authoritative and authoritarian) predicted attitudes towards criminal behaviour among the participants. The overall regression model was not significant, $F(6, 65) = 1.87$, $p = .099$. The model accounted for approximately 38% of the variance in attitudes towards criminal behaviour ($R^2 = .38$, adjusted $R^2 = .07$).

The multiple regression coefficients for all individual predictors were obtained via SPSS version 31 (see table 3).

Predictors	B	Standard error	B	T	P
Age	.01	.01	.23	1.89	.063
Emotional Intelligence Score	-.02	.11	-.02	-.16	.877
Permissive Parental Style	-.01	.10	-.01	-.09	.929
Authoritarian Parental Style	-.05	.09	-.10	-.62	.538
Authoritative Parental Style	.11	.08	.23	1.36	.179
Sex	.14	.21	.08	.65	.520

Table 3: the Multiple Regression Coefficients Predicting Attitudes Towards Criminal Behaviour (see appendix 2 for SPSS output).

The multiple regression analysis revealed that age, emotional intelligence, perceived parental style (authoritative, authoritarian and permissive) and sex did not significantly predict criminal behaviour attitudes.

Chapter 4: Discussion

The present study aimed to examine the relationship between perceived parental style, emotional intelligence and subsequent attitudes towards criminal behaviour, whilst also controlling for age and sex. The findings indicate a weak positive relationship between participant age and criminality attitudes, suggesting that older participants had less tolerance for offending behaviours. Weak negative relationships were also observed between both authoritative and authoritarian parenting and attitudes towards criminal behaviour. These correlations suggest greater flexibility in criminal attitudes among individuals who perceive their parents as authoritative or authoritarian. The multiple regression analysis was not significant, indicating that the unique predictors did not make a meaningful contribution to attitudes towards criminal behaviour when considered together. The research questions were not supported as emotional intelligence was not correlated with attitudes towards criminal behaviour, authoritarian and authoritative parenting did not predict stricter attitudes, and permissive parenting was not associated with attitudes towards offending. Taken together, the results highlight variation in criminal behaviour attitudes and the individual differences among participants, suggesting that the influence of parental style and emotional intelligence may operate differently across individuals and reflecting the complexity of these relationships.

The significant relationship observed between age and attitudes towards criminal behaviour may reflect differences within crime exposure as more time passes. As individuals age, they have greater life experiences, which may include encountering crime, either directly or indirectly through personal experiences, social networks or media exposure (Liu & Lachman, 2019). This increased exposure, combined with an increase in maturity, decision-making capacities and social responsibility, may shape less tolerance of crime due to a greater awareness of the consequences and impacts for individuals (Dewey, 2020; Scheibe & Carstensen, 2010). However, it is important to consider that repeated exposure may contribute to normalisation in some cases (Bandura, 1977), highlighting the complexity of the relationship between age and attitudes towards offending. Additionally, perceptions of social norms and accountability may shift across generations, meaning criminal behaviour attitudes may also reflect changing societal expectations rather than purely individual experience (Garcia et al., 2020). As outlined by previous literature, emotional and behavioural functioning continues to develop across the life span, with factors such as social environments, relationships and broader experiences playing important roles (Chapman & Hayslip, 2006). Therefore, this may suggest that age related differences in criminal attitudes are more likely to reflect accumulated experiences throughout time, rather than

being explained by a single underlying factor (Copp, Mumford & Taylor, 2025). Subsequently, the findings indicate increased exposure to crime across the lifespan may be a key contributor to the reported relationship between age and attitudes towards criminal behaviour.

Weak correlations were found between both authoritarian and authoritative parental styles and criminal attitudes, suggesting the participants had greater tolerance of offending in these parental styles. This limited strength expressed within this relationship may indicate parental style alone does not directly predict adult attitudes towards crime. Interestingly, the existing literature suggests authoritative parental style to have the least likelihood of criminality (Goering & Mrug, 2021), which is not supported within the present study as the outcomes were the same, in regard to attitudes, for authoritative and authoritarian parental styles. The differences highlighted throughout previous research between these two parenting styles (Bisby, Kimonis & Goulter, 2017; Kang & Guo, 2021) were expected to be apparent within the current study, however, the similarity within the outcomes suggests that parental style may not be as accurate in predicting attitudes towards offending as initially presumed. In authoritarian parenting specifically, compliance is often driven by fear (Schaffer, Clark & Jeglic, 2008), therefore responses within the current study could closer represent dishonesty based on fear of repercussion within the participants, despite its anonymity.

Additionally, parental influence may reduce over time making consistent assessment difficult across the lifespan (Copp, Mumford & Taylor, 2025). Whilst these weak correlations between perceived parental style and offending attitudes do exist, it can be arguable how direct these relationships are due to other experiences individuals may have (Slicker et al., 2005). Specifically, the present study analysed adults above 18 years of age with no higher end closing point; comparisons between younger and older adults may be problematic when considering parenting experience and may differ dramatically due to diluted parental influence with more time having passed (Schiebe & Carstensen, 2010; Sharma, 2017). This variance across ages could explain the non-significant multiple regression as adult life experiences such as personal relationships, employment and entering parenthood may alter the direct influence of parental style (Nastas & Sala, 2012; Chapman & Hayslip, 2006). However, this may not be universal as research suggests that early adversity can have lifelong effects on emotional intelligence, mental well-being and criminal behaviours (Hughes et al., 2016).

No significance was observed in relation to EI and attitudes towards criminal behaviour in this sample. This finding contrasts with previous literature linking lower EI to increased offending (Megreya, 2015; Sharma et al., 2015; Robertson, Daffern & Bucks, 2014). However, it may be explained by the present study exploring attitudes, as opposed to actual criminal actions (Day, 2009; Knight, 2005). It is also

worth considering that lower EI scores may be associated with reduced self-awareness (Mayer, Roberts & Barsade, 2008; Derkson, Kramer & Katzko, 2002) or response accuracy on self-report scales, especially regarding criminality. All participants were anonymous, but anonymity does not guarantee accurate self-reporting in practice (Hussein, Acquah & Musah, 2019). Therefore, some participants may have provided answers to the criminal attitudes scale that did not accurately reflect their true beliefs. Furthermore, the SSEIT (Schutte et al., 1998) used to assess EI within this study relies on self-report responses, which are subject to known limitations in reliability and response bias (Gignac et al., 2005). A further limitation of the current study is that participants completed the measures in uncontrolled home environments, increasing the risk of distraction, reduced engagement, and time pressure, which may have contributed to more superficial or rushed responses. The small sample size is also notable, as it may have reduced statistical power, and a larger more diverse participant pool could provide a more accurate representation of any associations; the contrast between genders is extreme, with most participants being female. This may aid explanation of the non-significant relationship as females are often reported to demonstrate greater empathy and emotional perception compared with males (Karimpour et al., 2019), which may be associated with lower tolerance towards criminal behaviour. Thus, the non-significant results between EI and attitudes towards offending may be explained by the restriction to attitudes specifically, limited accuracy in self-report measures, small sample size and a large contrast between genders.

The multiple regression analysis examining all predictors was not significant, indicating that none of the variables contributed unique explanatory power when considered together. This may be explained by the overlap between the predictors, as existing literature highlights that parenting style influences the development of EI (Nastas & Sala, 2012; Al-Elaimat, Adheisat & Alomyan, 2018; Harjis, 2025), with frameworks such as Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1977) suggesting that behaviours are learned through observation and imitation of caregivers, although the findings of the current study do not reflect this common reported overlap. Furthermore, the relationship between these factors is likely influenced by additional life experiences beyond perceived parenting, including adversity, personal relationships and employment (Chapman & Hayslip, 2006; Copp, Mumford & Taylor, 2025). Adversity specifically, may continue to contribute to long-term effects on emotional and behavioural development (Hughes et al., 2016), further complicating the ability to isolate unique predictors. All these elements may play a substantial role in shaping attitudes in adulthood, limiting the predictive strength of parental style and EI alone. Therefore, the non-significant regression model highlights the multifaceted and non-linear nature of attitudes towards offending, consistent with research suggesting that relationships between parenting, emotional development and behavioural outcomes are complex

(King, 2023). Thus, suggesting that these constructs cannot be adequately explained through a simple predictive model.

The current study presents limitations highlighting the need for caution when interpreting the results. The small, gender-imbalanced sample reduces the generalisability of the findings, therefore decreasing representation of the general population (Gupta et al., 2022; Weber et al., 2021). This could suggest that the real effects of these relationships are underestimated within the current findings, however, time-constraints and difficulty in recruiting participants explains the pool of individuals selected. Measurement limitations such as self-report scales may reduce the validity and reliability of the responses (Paulhus & Vazire, 2007), especially when completed in an uncontrolled environment such as personal devices. Participants may underreport socially undesirable attitudes, such as increased tolerance of crime, despite the anonymity provided. Additionally, self-reported EI scores potentially more closely represent perceived ability rather than actual ability (Brackett et al., 2006), therefore weakening or distorting correlations within the statistical analysis. Some participants may also misremember their experiences of being parented based upon current feelings and thoughts regarding their parents, even if their current mood is not necessarily related to early parental experience (Salmon & Reese, 2015). Therefore, the current parenting style variable may not be completely accurate, weakening its predictive value. Finally, this study focused solely on associations rather than cause-and-effect relationships so it cannot be determined whether any of the variables cause one another or the depth of interlinking between them. The limitations within this study represent challenges within the statistical power it holds; further exploration could implement alternative measurement approaches, more robust methodologies and larger, controlled samples to counteract these limitations.

Future research analysing perceived parental styles, EI and attitudes towards criminality could focus on longitudinal data to increase accuracy across the lifespan. This could track participants over time to explore whether parenting and EI scores influence attitudes across different life stages. This design could also examine the impact of external factors on these relationships. Further than this, including a more diverse sample (e.g. more males or different cultures) may present different findings. Exploration controlling for socioeconomic status, cultural parenting norms or ethnicity may provide a deeper understanding into the interactions between parental style, EI and offending attitudes (Gard et al., 2023; Williams, Priest & Anderson, 2016). Alternative measurement approaches could also be considered; behavioural EI tests instead of or in tandem with self-report materials may more accurately represent the actual EI level, not just the perceived one. Mixed methods, such as interviews or scenario-based measures could also increase the depth in which attitudes surrounding criminal behaviours are

understood. It may also be valuable to explore mediators between the variables such as life experiences, adversity, attachment, personality traits and peer influences (Martins et al., 2021; Haq, Shahed & Quraishi, 2024). These factors could moderate the relationship between parenting style and subsequent attitudes towards criminal behaviour, examining the interaction effects that the current study's regression could not detect. Future studies could compare these findings to actual criminal behaviour to determine whether the observed non-significant correlations are specific to attitudes or extend to behaviour.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

This study examined the relationship between perceived parental style, EI, and adult attitudes towards criminal behaviour. Overall, the findings indicate that parental style and EI did not significantly predict the conclusions and were only weakly associated with attitudes toward offending, while age also demonstrated a weak positive relationship with less tolerant attitudes. However, these findings are nuanced and may be context-dependent, emphasising the complexity of the relationships. The study highlights the importance of considering developmental and environmental factors when exploring attitudes towards offending, providing the foundation for longitudinal or more-specific studies in the future.

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Appendix 1 - Questionnaire

X.1. - Demographic Information.

Q1 – What is your age? (in years)

Q2 – What is your sex?

X.2 - The Schutte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test

Rate the following statements between 1 – strongly agree to 5 – strongly disagree

- I know when to speak about my personal problems to others
- When I am faced with obstacles, I remember times I faced similar obstacles and overcame them
- I expect that I will do well on most things I try
- Other people find it easy to confide in me
- I find it hard to understand the non-verbal messages of other people*
- Some of the major events of my life have led me to re-evaluate what is important and not important
- When my mood changes, I see new possibilities
- Emotions are one of the things that make my life worth living
- I am aware of my emotions as I experience them
- I expect good things to happen
- I like to share my emotions with others
- When I experience a positive emotion, I know how to make it last
- I arrange events others enjoy
- I seek out activities that make me happy
- I am aware of the non-verbal messages I send to others
- I present myself in a way that makes a good impression on others
- When I am in a positive mood, solving problems is easy for me
- By looking at their facial expressions, I recognize the emotions people are experiencing
- I know why my emotions change
- When I am in a positive mood, I am able to come up with new ideas
- I have control over my emotions
- I easily recognize my emotions as I experience them
- I motivate myself by imagining a good outcome to tasks I take on
- I compliment others when they have done something well
- I am aware of the non-verbal messages other people send
- When another person tells me about an important event in his or her life, I almost feel as though I have experienced this event myself
- When I feel a change in emotions, I tend to come up with new ideas
- When I am faced with a challenge, I give up because I believe I will fail*

- I know what other people are feeling just by looking at them
- I help other people feel better when they are down
- I use good moods to help myself keep trying in the face of obstacles
- I can tell how people are feeling by listening to the tone of their voice
- It is difficult for me to understand why people feel the way they do

X.3 - Attitudes towards criminal behaviour.

Rate the following criminal offences in terms of severity in your own opinion. 1 being not severe at all, 5 being very severe.

1. Tax fraud
2. Supplying alcohol to those under-age
3. Supplying/dealing illegal drugs
4. Burglary
5. Shoplifting
6. Animal abuse
7. Arson of domestic building
8. Arson of commercial building
9. Driving without a license/insurance
10. Identity theft
11. Carrying a dangerous weapon
12. Criminal damage
13. Cyber-stalking

2.4 - Parental Attitudes Questionnaire (PAQ) ¹

Rate the following statements in terms of how regularly you experienced this from immediate caregivers (1 being never, 5 being all of the time).

My caregiver used physical discipline in response to my behaviour.

My caregiver raised their voice, shouted, or used harsh language when responding to my behaviour.

My caregiver used critical or corrective comments to encourage me to change or improve my behaviour.

My caregiver removed privileges or access to preferred activities without giving me a clear explanation.

¹ Generative AI was used to support the development of some of the items included in this questionnaire to adjust the wording to more sensitive language.

My caregiver used time-out or separation from others as a consequence for my behaviour.

My caregiver sometimes stopped speaking to me or reduced interaction in response to my behaviour.

My caregiver was generally responsive to my feelings and needs.

My caregiver offered comfort and understanding when I was upset.

My caregiver helped me understand the consequences of my behaviour.

My caregiver took my needs into account when making plans.

My caregiver offered praise or positive feedback.

My caregiver expressed warmth and affection toward me.

My caregiver sometimes set consequences but did not always follow through.

My caregiver sometimes changed decisions when I became upset or angry.

My caregiver appeared to find disciplinary situations difficult.

My caregiver sometimes described our relationship as being very close, like 'best friends'.

My caregiver sometimes provided extra material items or treats.

My caregiver found it challenging at times to set or maintain boundaries.

Appendix 2 – SPSS Output

Y.1 – Descriptive Statistics.

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Criminal_Behaviour_Attitudes	101	2.23	5.00	4.1307	.56569
AGE	73	17.00	70.00	39.0548	12.75941
Emotional_Intelligence_Score	102	1.38	4.39	2.7129	.62676
Permissive	102	.00	5.00	2.2498	.84451
Authoritarian	102	.00	5.00	2.7861	1.09847
Authoritative	102	.33	5.00	3.1235	1.27953
What is your sex? - Selected Choice	102	1	3	1.90	.330
Valid N (listwise)	72				

Y.2 – Correlation Matrix.

Correlations								
		What is your sex? - Selected Choice	Criminal_Behaviour_Attitudes	AGE	Emotional_Intelligence_Score	Permissive	Authoritarian	Authoritative
What is your sex? - Selected Choice	Pearson Correlation	1	.056	.165	.094	.115	.171	-.151
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.578	.162	.346	.251	.086	.131
	N	102	101	73	102	102	102	102
Criminal_Behaviour_Attitudes	Pearson Correlation	.056	1	.249*	-.095	.085	-.201*	.212*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.578		.035	.346	.397	.044	.033
	N	101	101	72	101	101	101	101
AGE	Pearson Correlation	.165	.249*	1	-.122	-.095	-.107	-.050
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.162	.035		.302	.426	.370	.673
	N	73	72	73	73	73	73	73
Emotional_Intelligence_Score	Pearson Correlation	.094	-.095	-.122	1	-.001	.171	-.151
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.346	.346	.302		.992	.087	.130
	N	102	101	73	102	102	102	102
Permissive	Pearson Correlation	.115	.085	-.095	-.001	1	.256**	.251*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.251	.397	.426	.992		.009	.011
	N	102	101	73	102	102	102	102
Authoritarian	Pearson Correlation	.171	-.201*	-.107	.171	.256**	1	-.526**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.086	.044	.370	.087	.009		<.001
	N	102	101	73	102	102	102	102
Authoritative	Pearson Correlation	-.151	.212*	-.050	-.151	.251*	-.526**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.131	.033	.673	.130	.011	<.001	
	N	102	101	73	102	102	102	102

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
 **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Y.3 – Multiple Regression.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.384 ^a	.147	.069	.57589

a. Predictors: (Constant), What is your sex? - Selected Choice, Permissive, Emotional_Intelligence_Score, AGE, Authoritarian, Authoritative

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3.730	6	.622	1.874	.099 ^b
	Residual	21.557	65	.332		
	Total	25.287	71			

a. Dependent Variable: Criminal_Behaviour_Attitudes

b. Predictors: (Constant), What is your sex? - Selected Choice, Permissive, Emotional_Intelligence_Score, AGE, Authoritarian, Authoritative

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.264	.624		5.230	<.001
	AGE	.011	.006	.229	1.894	.063
	Emotional_Intelligence_Score	-.017	.110	-.019	-.156	.877
	Permissive	-.009	.101	-.012	-.089	.929
	Authoritarian	-.054	.087	-.100	-.619	.538
	Authoritative	.106	.078	.226	1.358	.179
	What is your sex? - Selected Choice	.136	.211	.080	.646	.520

a. Dependent Variable: Criminal_Behaviour_Attitudes

Y.4 – Cronbach's Alpha

Reliability

Scale: Authoritative

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	99	97.1
	Excluded ^a	3	2.9
	Total	102	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.938	6

Scale: Authoritarian

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	85	83.3
	Excluded ^a	17	16.7
	Total	102	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.748	5

Scale: Permissive

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	84	82.4
	Excluded ^a	18	17.6
	Total	102	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.669	6